

REFLECTION AS A MECHANISM FOR IMPLEMENTING COGNITIVE COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS OF PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES

G. Amanova

Department of Pedagogy, Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

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Abstract. *The article touches upon the problem of the need to develop reflection in the implementation of cognitive competence of future teachers. The effectiveness of a good teacher is a combination of a variety of knowledge, reflective skills and competencies that are constantly developing and enriched. In our opinion, the most significant of them are showing respect for others, sympathy and empathy. Reflection is a necessary condition for the growth of both a professional and a teacher's personality. This paper focuses on the content of the reflective process and its impact on the development of psychological and pedagogical competencies, as well as how it functions. The analysis of various approaches to understanding the structure of activity and the content of reflection associated with it was used as a research tool. Regardless of the chosen model of psychological and pedagogical activity, its effective implementation requires reflection - the ability of a teacher to comprehend the educational process and his own experience, which is one of the key factors in his professional and personal improvement. The accumulated practical experience of teachers is not a sufficient condition for professional development. Only through constant reflection, analysis and transformation of their own experiences did they develop their skills.*

Keywords: *competence, reflection, cognitive competence, reflection mechanisms, creative approach.*

Introduction

The formation of reflection found a key expression in philosophy with the emergence of fundamental concepts of knowledge, which were then formalized into a separate area - the theory of knowledge. Within the framework of this theory, understanding is defined as an independent, creative action carried out by a person. This act of understanding is a transformation of the internal state, a transition from one state to another, accompanied by the acquisition of understanding. As a result, a person's abilities to perceive, comprehend, remember and emotionally experience expand.

What is the essence of the psychological content of reflection? The extensive and multifaceted nature of the psychological content of reflection, its multifunctionality, a variety of features and properties emphasize the significance and special role of reflection in the integral structure of the human personality. Reflexive processes affect almost all aspects of psychological reality. The development of reflexive psychology is closely associated with the name of A. Busemann, who at the beginning of the 20th century was the first to single it out as an independent scientific discipline. The term "reflection" itself comes from the late Latin "reflexio", which literally translates as "return, reflection". Currently, scientific approaches to the study of reflexive processes are being formed in various fields of psychology [6].

Reflection plays an important role in creative and intellectual work, helping to set goals, form adequate expectations of oneself, taking into account external requirements and the specifics of a particular situation. In modern pedagogy, the priority is the development of the personality of participants in the educational process, and since this process is internal and can be assessed primarily by the person himself, it is reflection, as an act of self-observation and self-analysis, that allows us to assess progress. In training, reflective skills help participants structure and document the results of development and self-development, as well as identify the causes of success or failure in this process.

Western social psychology began to study reflection with the works of J. Holmes, T. Newcomb and C. Cooley, focusing on experiments with pairs of people interacting in specially created laboratory conditions. Scientists believe that for a more complete disclosure of the essence of reflection, it should be analyzed not in a duet, but as part of large, structured social groups connected by common, important work for them.

Reflection includes not only self-understanding, self-knowledge, but also the process of understanding and evaluating another. With its help, it is possible to achieve correlation of one's consciousness, opinions, values with the opinions, values, relationships of other people, groups, society, and humanity as a whole. It is the ability to reflect that enables a person to form images and meanings of life, actions, and block ineffective interpretations. The most important feature of reflection is their ability to manage their own activity in accordance with personal values and meanings, to form and switch to new mechanisms in connection with changed conditions, goals, and tasks of activity. Reflection ensures understanding of the past and anticipation of the future [10].

The conditions and means of developing reflection in educational activities identified during the study of scientific research are summarized in Table 1.

Analysis of modern research allows us to determine the conditions for developing reflection, special requirements for the organization of educational material and the educational process as a whole, the dependence of the development process on the nature and content of the learning process. The development of reflection is based on adherence to the principles of developmental learning and the use of a set of pedagogical means of targeted influence on the formation of this ability.

Table 1

Conditions and means of developing reflection in educational activities

Conditions for the development of reflection	Means of formation of reflection
1. Formation of motivational readiness for the development of reflective abilities	Organization of special interaction with the student to discover the meaning and motivational significance of reflection, development of a conscious desire to focus on the process and results of mental activity

<p>2. Knowledge of the structure and content of educational activities by students, the presence of ideas about effective ways of regulating them</p>	<p>Assimilation of a set of methodological knowledge: about the structure of activities, types of scientific thinking, logical principles underlying scientific knowledge, logic of evidence and explanations. System of external requirements for the organization of activities</p>
<p>3. Overcoming absorption in one's own activity, providing an analytical position for performing additional mental actions</p>	<p>Involving students in dialogues, debates, contradictory situations, dialogue mode, conversation method, transition to a position of new activity through modeling situations of future professional activity, putting the student in the role of a teacher. Combining the analysis of the subject content of the activity with the analysis of one's own methods of activity (sign-symbolic, structural-logical schemes, generalizing tables for structuring large sections of the studied material)</p>
<p>4. Teaching intellectual self-regulation</p>	<p>Development of conscious self-control actions (analysis of goals, conditions, methods, results, teaching self-assessment, correcting mistakes, stimulating self-analysis processes). Development of scientifically based teaching aids that perform organizational, control and management functions, creating conditions for self-control, self-correction, activation of educational activities (specially formulated questions, self-control algorithms). Development of self-observation processes, tracking the presence or absence of knowledge, the habit of evaluating results</p>
<p>5. Development of the creative component of thinking</p>	<p>Stimulation of independent formulation of scientific problems in developmental learning. The presence of problem situations that are solved together, taking into account the results of individual creative activity</p>

6. Developmental content of control forms	Replacing the system of marks with a system of criteria, formulating examination questions that focus not on reproducing the finished, but on finding a solution to the task at hand. Examination as a practical activity of a specialist, a set of basic actions included in the future specialty
7. Implementation of the principles of systematicity and problematization in combination with the use of reflection as a method in each step of professional activity	Game-based learning (organizational development games), group work (knowledge exchange, interpersonal skills), imitation of professional activity, solving educational and production problems
8. Subject-subject interaction and live communication	Dialogue forms of work, tasks for awareness of the following development goals, setting goals for self-development, encouraging the expression of actions in words

Self-control, self-assessment, and reflection are the most important stages of learning activities. It is the mastery of these actions that allows students to independently plan, analyze, and evaluate their own activities, make adjustments, set new learning tasks for themselves, and find ways to solve them. Systematic work on developing these actions ultimately leads to an increase in the level of mastery of the educational material, and to a transition to a new stage of development.

Materials and methods

To study the level of reflexivity, we used the methodology of A.V. Karpov, we analyzed the data of 1st-3rd year students and obtained the following results. A low level of reflexivity was found in 33.8% of future teachers who took part in the study. Students with a low level of reflexivity, as a rule, experience difficulties with planning their activities, are prone to stereotypical thinking, do not demonstrate the ability to analyze previously made mistakes, do not know how to use the acquired successful or unsuccessful experience. have difficulty overcoming difficult situations, as well as analyzing the current situation. A student with a low level of reflexivity has difficulty regulating his behavior. The average level of reflexivity development was noted in 60% of respondents. The average level of reflexivity implies the ability to plan your actions, correctly assess the current situation, analyze your own actions, as well as the actions of others, is characterized by self-esteem, self-management, self-expression, self-awareness, reflexive and critical thinking, however, reflexive processes can be chaotic, and reflexive analysis superficial. A high level of reflection development was revealed in 6.1% of students who took part in the study. Students who demonstrated a high level of thinking development have well-developed social and personal mechanisms of self-awareness, understanding of themselves and others, they are characterized by rational, critical, multifaceted, intellectual thinking, they are more inclined to analyze their own activities, as well as the actions of others, to determine the causes and consequences of their previous, current and future actions.

They know how to plan their actions and predict possible consequences, make non-standard decisions leading to an effective solution to the tasks. Comparing the diagnostic indicators for determining the level of reflexivity of 1st, 2nd and 3rd year students, we observe an

insignificant difference on the scale corresponding to a low level of reflection development: 38.6% of 1st year students had a low level of reflection development, 23% of 2nd year students, and 15% of 3rd year students had a low level of reflection. Positive dynamics of reflection development is observed between 2nd and 3rd year students. There is also a difference in the scale corresponding to the average level of reflection development: 1st year students - 61.4%, 2nd year students - 56.4%, 3rd year students - 57.5%, which also indicates positive dynamics. High indicators of the level of reflection were not found among 1st year students. Positive dynamics of reflection development is observed between 2nd and 3rd year students. At the same time, there is a significant difference in the results on the scale corresponding to a high level of reflexivity development: 14.6% of 2nd year students and 27.5% of 3rd year students. Taking into account the results of the study, it can be said that the level of reflexivity among 3rd year students is 27.5% higher than the level of reflexivity among 1st year students (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Level of reflection in students.

Conclusions

Requirements for the level of training of teaching staff are increasing every year. Today, in the context of the introduction of a credit-modular system in universities, the professionalism of a teacher is expressed in his competence, which allows him to effectively carry out his own individual activities. It is no longer necessary to simply reproduce previously mastered patterns and methods of functioning, but to develop new, creative approaches, as well as constant self-development, both professionally and personally.

The development of cognitive reflection in teachers plays a key role in their professional and personal growth. At each stage of the development of the teacher's professional self-awareness, intellectual reflection acts as a means of overcoming inevitable crisis moments. The level of intellectual development of the teacher determines his ability to reflect, which is necessary for an objective analysis of information received from students. Only a teacher with developed intellectual reflection can effectively resolve personal conflicts and continuously improve in a dynamically changing educational space.

REFERENCES

1. Bekhoeva A. A. Psychological and pedagogical characteristics of the levels of professional reflection in students of future teachers // National Psychological Journal. - 2015. - No. 17. - P. 05-110.
2. Budnikova S. P. Development of reflection as a component of professional subjectivity in the process of training future teachers // Bulletin of MGOU. - 2019. - No. 4. - P. 91-103. [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://vestnik-mgou.ru/Articles/Doc/13424>
3. Karpov A. V., Ponomareva V. V. Psychology of reflexive control mechanisms. - M., IP RAS, 2000.
4. Karpov A. V., Skityaeva I. M. Psychology of reflection. - M.: IP RAS, 2002.
5. Karpov AV, Skityaeva IM Psychology of metacognitive processes of personality. - M.: IP RAS, 2005.
6. Karpov AV Reflexivity as a mental property and methods of its diagnostics // Psychological journal - 2003. - Vol. 24. - No. 5. – P. 45-57.
7. Karpov AV Psychology of reflexive mechanisms of activity. - M.: IP RAS, 2004.
8. Karpov AV On some patterns of the relationship between thinking and metathinking // Practical thinking: theoretical foundations and applied aspects. - Yaroslavl: Yaroslavl State University, 2008. – P. 31-86.
9. Cognitive psychology / Ed. VN Druzhinin, DV Ushakova. - M.: PER SE, 2002.10. Сафин В.Ф. Динамика оценочных эталонов в подростковом и юношеском возрасте / Вопросы психологии. 2000 - №1 - с.69-75
1. 11 Dixon R.A. Structure and development of metamemory in adulthood // Jour. of Gerontology. – 1983. - 38. - Pp. 682-688.
2. 12. Lemba, L. L. Pedagogical reflection as an element of professional competence of a teacher / L. L. Lemba. - Text: direct // Young scientist. - 2020. - No. 46 (336). - P. 537-540. - URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/336/75123/>
3. 13. Metacognition: Cognitive and Social Dimensions / Ed. By V. Yzerbyt et al. - SAGE Publications, 2002.
4. 14. Metcalfe J., Shimamura A.P. (Eds.). Metacognition: Knowing about Knowing. - Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. 1994.
5. 15. Flavell J.H. Speculations about the nature and development of metacognition. In F.E. Weinert and R.H. Kluwe (Eds.). Metacognition, Motivation, and Understanding. - Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 1987.